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EXPLORING FOOD CHOICES AND ROUTINE FACTORS AS DRIVERS OF FOOD WASTE BEHAVIOR AMONG PAKISTANI UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

Food waste is a pressing global issue with significant economic, environmental and social damages. Young consumers are one of the largest source of preventable food waste. This study explores the food choice factors and food consumption patterns (routine factors) of university students in Pakistan and their intricate relationship with food waste behavior. Qualitative approach was adopted to discover the deep-rooted underlying factors that triggers food waste. 30 in-depth interviews were conducted from the three stakeholders i.e., university students, parents of university students and university food management authorities. Data were analyzed in detail, and several themes and patterns have been extracted. Findings reveal complex interplay of food choices including sensory appeal, moods and emotional state, financial constraint, health consciousness, lack of ethical concern and convenience among university students. Moreover, routine factors such as food portions, routine and time constraint, distrust in food safety & hygiene and company of friends significantly impact food waste generation. The research has contributed literature by offering a nuanced understanding of determinants of food waste behavior. The pragmatic insight offered in this study can assist in developing interventions for changing student attitudes towards food waste and guiding university policies. The results will also be useful in developing a quantitative model for future studies.

Keywords: Food choice factors, food consumption patterns, in-depth interviews university students, food waste behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Amid the rising global concerns surrounding food insecurity and environmental degradation, the often-overlooked issue of food waste, especially among educated youth it has emerged as a critical challenge that requires immediate attention. With the integration of advanced technology across sectors, including the food supply chain, food has become more readily accessible than ever before. This abundance has inadvertently contributed to excessive and careless consumption patterns, intensifying sustainability challenges (Nikolaus, Richardson, & Ellison, 2018; Shabbir et al., 2024). While numerous countries have pledged commitments to sustainable development and environmental protection, their approaches to mitigating the environmental consequences of food waste remain inconsistent. Tackling food waste is increasingly recognized as a pivotal strategy for ensuring environmental sustainability and food security (Cheng, Zhang, & Li, 2024).

A large body of literature on food waste has centered around production, logistics, and retail-level inefficiencies. However, there is growing recognition that waste at the consumer level particularly among young adults in educational institutions constitutes a substantial portion of the problem (Hebrok & Boks, 2017). Prior studies suggest that a majority of food waste occurs at the consumption stage, with consumers accounting for over 60% of avoidable food waste globally, across both developed and developing countries (Nikolaus et al., 2018). According to Kaur et al. (2020), consumer food waste is largely driven by behavioral, contextual, and demographic factors. Key contributors include oversized portions and insufficient time allocated for eating, both of which are common in fast-paced, convenience-oriented settings.

Younger generation especially university students often prioritize convenience over sustainability, unintentionally adopting habits that promote food waste. Their eating behaviors directly influence the volume of waste generated in institutional food settings

such as dining halls and cafeterias. Additional factors contributing to waste in these environments include inaccurate food labeling, varied appetites, and specific dietary preferences. Furthermore, demographic attributes particularly gender have been associated with waste behavior; for instance, research suggests that male students tend to waste less staple food compared to females (Wu et al., 2019). Age also plays a critical role, with younger individuals generally wasting more food than older adults. This tendency may stem from increased spontaneity, a stronger preference for convenience, limited experience in food management, and different approaches to evaluating trade-offs (Nikolaus et al., 2018).

Economic conditions also influences the wasteful behavior as students with greater financial flexibility tend to waste more food, whereas those with tighter budgets often demonstrate more mindful consumption patterns (Wu et al., 2019; Steen et al., 2018). Although food consumption behavior have been widely examined in household contexts, their manifestation within institutional settings such as universities have received comparatively less scholarly attention, despite the distinct behavioral dynamics at play (Stancu et al., 2016). In this regard, daily routine factors warrant deeper investigation to understand how time constraints, scheduling conflicts, and habitual practices shape student's waste-related behaviors. Furthermore, food choices themselves play a significant role in food disposal decisions and are worth exploring as antecedents of attitude within a qualitative framework (Stefan et al., 2013).

In Pakistan, food waste is a paradoxical concern. On one hand, food is culturally and religiously valued as a blessing that must not be wasted; on the other hand, rising urbanization, shifting lifestyles, and increased access to ready-made meals have led to noticeable changes in consumption patterns especially among university students. Despite this, empirical studies exploring food waste behavior among Pakistani youth remain limited, and those that exist are mostly quantitative in nature, focusing on awareness and attitudes (Bhatti et al., 2023; Jilani et al., 2021). There is little qualitative insight into the everyday routines, preferences, and contextual factors that shape how students make food-related decisions and engage in waste behaviors. This gap is particularly important in the context of universities, where students often live independently for the first time, make autonomous food choices, and face constraints such as tight schedules, limited budgets, and institutional food systems. Their behavior is embedded in a complex web of food preferences, time management routines, peer influence, and institutional norms, all of which may contribute to food waste in distinct ways. Yet these contextual and subjective experiences remain under explored in the Pakistani context.

After thorough review of literature it was revealed that there is lack of evidence for understanding the routine factors and food preference of university students. As multiple reviews highlights scarcity of qualitative studies on psychographics, cultural values, and food-waste drivers especially in non-Western or non-WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic) settings like Pakistan. These studies emphasize that quantitative surveys alone are insufficient to understand the local meanings and practices. Along with that a systematic review on food waste at educational institutions found that most studies are quantitative and geographically concentrated in Western countries, with very few qualitative explorations of university settings in developing nations (Kaur et al., 2020). While research often examines general food waste drivers in Pakistan, they focus on awareness, guilt, or environmental concern, with

limited attention to how food preferences or daily habits shape attitudes and waste patterns. Quantitative studies have found factors like time pressure and religiosity influence food-waste attitudes among Pakistani youth. However, there is no qualitative work detailing how student's routines, schedules, and management strategies manifest in everyday waste behaviors (Stefan et al., 2013; Bhatti et al., 2023).

Hence, this paper embarks to explore the drivers (here defined as factors that cause a specific behavior to take place or develop) that plays a significant role in understanding the food waste behavior. The present study adopts a qualitative, constructivist interpretive approach to explore food waste behaviors among university students in Pakistan. Conceptually informed by an extended version of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the study examines how food choice factors shape student's attitudes toward waste and how routine-related factors may operate as independent drivers of food disposal behaviors. Unlike traditional TPB studies, this research does not seek to test causal pathways, but rather to understand how students, their families, and university staff interpret and make sense of food waste within their daily lives. By doing so, an enhanced comprehension is created which depicts the drivers which help people to reduce their food waste within universities and will help in exploring the perceptions, choices, routine and behaviors related to wasted food among university student through in-depth interviews.

By engaging students, parents, and university authorities through in-depth interviews, the study aims to provide a rich, multi-perspective understanding of the meanings, motivations, and constraints that influence food waste in university settings. The insights generated may contribute to more context-sensitive strategies for food waste reduction and inform institutional and policy-level interventions in the education sector.

OBJECTIVES

1. How does food preferences and choices influence the food waste among university students in Pakistan?
2. What role do daily routines play in shaping food consumption and waste behaviors among Pakistani university students?
3. How do students understand and explain their food waste behaviors within the context of their daily life patterns, institutional environment, and peer culture?

LITERATURE REVIEW

A substantial body of literature has explored the underlying drivers and measurement approaches related to food waste, with particular emphasis on consumer behavior as a key contributing factor (Ananda, Karunasena, & Pearson, 2023). Numerous studies have examined these drivers to inform the development of effective and sustainable policy interventions aimed at food waste reduction. In recent years, food waste prevention has garnered significant global attention, particularly in the context of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, which call for halving per capita global food waste by 2030. Achieving this target is considered a critical step toward addressing climate change and enhancing environmental sustainability (Soorani & Ahmadvand, 2019).

Research on the drivers of consumer-generated food waste has primarily examined behavioral routines such as shopping, food ordering, meal planning, and practices related to leftovers and food reuse both in domestic and out-of-home dining contexts. While these studies offer valuable insights, they remain far from comprehensive, revealing notable gaps in both conceptual depth and analytical scope. Much of the

existing work has centered on cognitive factors, particularly normative beliefs and individual attitudes, to explain food waste behavior (Jabeen, Dhir, Islam, Talwar, & Papa, 2023).

An international review of 52 higher education institutions revealed that 60% of universities do not track food waste generated in their canteens, highlighting a critical data gap (Shaukat & Rehman, 2021). This lack of monitoring limits our ability to assess the full scale of food waste, understand its environmental and economic impacts, or implement effective mitigation strategies (Akhter et al., 2024; Kausar et al., 2022).

Globally, the total volume of food waste has reached alarming levels, particularly in contexts where food is produced in bulk such as social gatherings, restaurants, and institutional hostels. Recent research has drawn attention to daily food waste in student hostels, attributing it to behaviors such as excessive self-serving, unrealistic consumption standards, and an unregulated abundance of food availability (Rajalakshmi & Harshavardhini, 2024; Chaudhary, 2025).

In developing countries like Pakistan, food waste remains prevalent despite widespread food insecurity. Bhatti et al. (2023) observed that young consumers often discard food due to factors like social conformity, over-preparation, and poor planning. However, in-depth investigations specifically focused on university settings remain scarce, indicating a need for further research to explore the contextual and behavioral dynamics of food waste in higher education institutions.

Theoretical Understanding

Several theories have been used to understand the food waste behavior. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Norm Activation Model (NAM) are the most common theories that has been used to study wasteful behavior. TPB has been widely implemented to predict and explain a wide variety of environmental behaviors. A meta-analysis conducted by Klockner (2013) revealed that around 40% of published studies in the field of environmental psychology utilized the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as their foundational framework. Additionally, TPB has been effectively employed as a theoretical basis in hospitality research, including studies on consumer's intentions to dine at eco-friendly restaurants, stay in environmentally sustainable hotels, or spend on green products and services (Gao, Mattila, & Lee, 2016; Kang, Stein, Heo, & Lee, 2012), food ordering decision-making process in the restaurant. Hence, we assumed that the TPB was adaptable to explain the consumer's food waste behavior and an extension of TPB can also be done by exploring new factors as it has been previously done by Mughal, Thogersen & Faisal (2023). TPB can be extended by exploring the attitudinal factors. Attitude, a key predictor of intention, reflects individual's overall evaluation of a specific behavior (Greaves et al., 2013). Karim et al. (2013) found that attitude exerted the most significant influence on behavioral intention. It represents the general positive or negative judgment toward a given behavior. As noted by Ajzen (1991), the more favorable the attitude, the stronger the intention to engage in that behavior. Both the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) recognize attitude as a crucial determinant of behavior, typically mediated through intention. Attitudes are shaped by consistent or conflicting beliefs about the outcomes of a behavior (Povey et al., 2001; Tourangeau et al., 1991) and significantly affect one's intention to either perform or avoid a specific action. Numerous studies confirm that attitude serves as a vital antecedent to behavioral intention (Ajzen, 1991; Povey et al., 2001; Tourangeau et al.,

1991). For instance, Kaiser et al. (1999) identified attitude as the most influential predictor of behavioral intentions. The attitude–behavior relationship has been examined across various dimensions. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is a widely used model to predict and understand consumer behaviors, including food waste. The model posits that behavior is shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Research applying TPB to food waste has highlighted the role of moral norms and intention (Greaves et al., 2013; Mughal et al., 2023), though many studies focus on attitudes without accounting for structural and habitual influences.

Recent extensions of TPB attempt to incorporate non-deliberative and routine-based factors, acknowledging that much of food waste occurs through habitual, non-reflective action (Stancu et al., 2016; Stefan et al., 2013). In this vein, the current study adopts an expanded view of TPB, treating food choice factors as antecedents to attitudes and routine factors (e.g., time pressure, daily structure) as parallel influences on food waste behaviors. In the present study, attitude is further explored by examining how food choice factors influence food waste behavior, while food consumption patterns considered as routine influences, are investigated concurrently to gain a deeper understanding of wasteful food practices.

Food Choices

Food choice is a complex, multi-dimensional process shaped by taste, health, culture, convenience, and social influences (Furst et al., 1996). Among young adults, preferences often shift toward convenience and impulsivity, increasing the likelihood of over-ordering or discarding unwanted food (Nikolaus et al., 2018).

Individuals construct personal food systems, cognitive frameworks that shape their food choices and guide eating behavior within specific contexts. These decisions are inherently dynamic, evolving both across historical eras and throughout an individual's lifespan. The food-related choices made by earlier generations differ significantly from those of today and will continue to change in the future. On a more immediate scale, food decisions also fluctuate across daily, weekly, seasonal, and yearly cycles. This complexity arises from the multifaceted nature of food decisions, which involve deliberations about what, when, where, and with whom to eat (Griffin et al., 2009).

Personal food systems encompass several elements: the formation and negotiation of food choice values, categorization of foods and eating contexts, and the development of strategies, routines, and scripts to manage recurring decisions. These food choice values such as taste, cost, health, convenience, and social relationships are influenced by individual meanings and emotional associations. To streamline decision-making, individuals categorize foods and eating situations based on their characteristics, contextual factors, or personal experiences and preferences (Kausar et al., 2021).

The life course perspective further enriches this understanding by highlighting ongoing, dynamic processes such as trajectories, transitions or turning points, timing, and contextual influences. Trajectories represent enduring patterns of thought, emotion, and behavior related to food that accumulate and shape future choices. For instance, early exposure to family food traditions and preferences can create a food upbringing that anchors long-term eating identities and roles. Conversely, turning points such as adopting a restrictive diet after a medical event like heart bypass surgery can dramatically reshape food behavior.

A wide range of factors influences food choices. Drawing on qualitative interviews, Furst

et al. (1996) identified five key domains: cultural ideals, individual preferences, available resources, social influences, and situational contexts. These factors are embedded within and shaped by the life course, interacting with each other to inform the personal construction of food-related decisions.

Visscher's et al. (2016) suggested that there are several food choice factors which impacts the food waste attitude including health, price, sensory appeals, moods, ethical concerns, convenience and many others. Even though multiple food choice factors have been identified (Cunha et al., 2018) but have not been identified to measure its role in building or changing attitude (Stefan et al., 2013). In university contexts, students often experience greater autonomy in food decision-making but also face challenges such as limited cooking skills and inconsistent meal routines (Parizeau et al., 2015). These factors can lead to mismatches between intention and consumption, resulting in waste. Cultural norms and values transmitted through family (Koivupuro et al., 2012; Zaro, 2017) also influence perceptions of food waste and acceptable disposal practices.

Food Consumption Patterns

There are several factors that influence the food waste behaviors with differing roles in reducing and/or increasing waste as discussed in prior literature (Nikolaus et al., 2018; Stancu et al., 2013). Routine and structural constraints are emerging as critical, yet underexplored, drivers of food waste. Stancu et al. (2016) propose two distinct paths to waste: a deliberative route (e.g., poor planning or lack of awareness) and a routine-based route (e.g., habits, time scarcity, and forgetfulness). Students frequently navigate both: they may intend to reduce waste but are limited by tight schedules, irregular eating habits, and institutional food systems (Nikolaus et al., 2018; Stefan et al., 2013).

Some of the routine factors which have been explored in the household context includes portion size, sensory value, social influence, connection/disconnection with preparer etc. Consumer behavior and attitudes towards food are fundamental determinants of food waste. Research by Stancu, Haugaard, and Lahteenmaki (2016) suggests that individual's attitudes towards food waste, perceived value of food, and awareness of consequences significantly impact their disposal behaviors. In institutional settings such as universities, shared meals, buffet-style dining, or pre-set portions often lead to over consumption or uneaten leftovers (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015; Quested et al., 2013). Yet few studies consider the perspectives of university staff involved in food provision and management, a gap this study seeks to address through multi-stakeholder interviews. Meal planning and preparation routines significantly influence food waste behavior. Research indicates that individuals with structured meal planning routines tend to waste less food compared to those with spontaneous cooking habits (Kausar & Qayyum, 2018). Moreover, cooking skills, time constraints, and convenience-oriented food choices impact the likelihood of food waste occurrence during meal preparation (Koivupuro et al., 2012). Efficient storage practices play a crucial role in reducing food waste at the household level (Zubair et al., 2025). Studies have shown that improper storage techniques, such as inadequate temperature control and improper use of refrigeration, contribute to premature food spoilage and waste (Parizeau et al., 2015). Additionally, factors like packaging design and labeling accuracy influence consumers' ability to store food effectively and extend its shelf life (Russell et al., 2017). Social and environmental factors within individuals' routines can shape food waste behavior. Peer influence, social norms, and household dynamics impact food-related decisions and

disposal practices (Schanes et al., 2018). Moreover, environmental awareness, access to recycling facilities, and local waste management policies influence individuals' motivations to reduce food waste and engage in sustainable consumption practices (Martinez-Sanchez et al., 2016; Taymoor et al., 2025).

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design underpinned by a constructivist interpretive paradigm, which assumes that reality is socially constructed and that individuals create meanings based on their experiences, interactions, and cultural contexts. Rather than seeking objective truths or causal explanations, this approach emphasizes understanding how people interpret their daily behaviors and the meanings they assign to them.

A constructivist lens is particularly appropriate for this study, which explores food waste as a socially and contextually embedded behavior shaped by food choices, daily routines, and institutional settings. The study is conceptually informed by an extended version of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), treating food choice factors as antecedents to attitude formation and routine-related factors as parallel influences on food waste behavior. However, the analysis remained open-ended and grounded in participant’s own interpretations, in line with the inductive nature of qualitative research (Cresswell, 2013).

In-depth interviews are especially befitting for addressing sensitive topics that people might feel reluctant to discuss in a group (Milena, Dainora & Alin, 2008).

Participants and Sampling

Participants were selected through purposive sampling, targeting individuals with relevant experiences and perspectives on food related behaviors in the university context. As information rich individuals, who deal with issues of central importance, can provide the insights for developing in-depth understanding of less explored issues (Patton, 2015). A sample of 30 participants have been selected. Data were collected in the time frame of, September 2023 to February 2024. However, the interviews through the laddering technique were started from general questions and preceded in accordance with consumer’s replies. The study included three groups:

University students including both hostel residents and day scholars from diverse academic backgrounds, socioeconomic statuses, and dietary preferences. Parents of university students and operational Staff (Food and Hostel Services) including hostel managers, cafeteria staff, and student affairs personnel who engage with students’ food consumption patterns and institutional food waste management. Participants were recruited from both public and private sector universities of Pakistan which enabled insights into varying institutional environments and student demographics.

The detailed lists of participants is provided below:

Table 1: Interview Details of Students

Respondents	Gender	Education level	University	Interview Dates	Inducted/ location
1	Female	PhD	PMAS Agriculture university Rawalpindi	24-8-2023	Rawalpindi
2	Female	MS	University of Azad	9-10-2023	Rawalpindi

3	Female	BBA	Jammu Kashmir Muzafarabad BUIITEMS	and	19-10- 2023	Islamabad
4	Male	Law	University Peshawar	of	2-11-2023	Peshawar
5	Female	MBA	Quaid-e-Azam University		21-11- 2023	Islamabad
6	Female	BBA	University Karachi	of	14-9-2023	Karachi
7	Male	BS (IT)	University Punjab	of	9-1-2024	Lahore
8	Male	MA (Education)	Karakoram International university Gilgit		26-10- 2023	Islamabad
9	Male	MBA	IBA (Sakkhar)		17-1-2024	Islamabad
10	Male	MA (English Literature)	NUML		11-1-2024	Islamabad

Table 2: *Interview details of parents*

Respondents	Gender	University	Interview dates	Inducted/ location
1	Female	PMAS Arid Agriculture university Rawalpindi	29-8-2023	Rawalpindi
2	Female	University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir Muzafarabad	9-10-2023	Rawalpindi
3	Female	BUIITEMS	19-10-2023	Rawalpindi
4	Male	University of Peshawar	2-11-2023	Peshawar
5	Female	Quaid-e-Azam University	22-11-2023	Islamabad
6	Male	University of Karachi	18-9-2023	Karachi
7	Male	University of Punjab	9-1-2024	Lahore
8	Male	Karakoram International university Gilgit	26-10-2023	Rawalpindi
9	Female	IBA (Sakkhar)	17-1-2024	Rawalpindi
10	Female	NUML	25-1-2024	Islamabad

Table 3: *Interview details of Operational Staff (Food and Hostel Services)*

Respondents	Designation	University	Interview dates	Inducted/ location
1	Mess charge	In PMAS Arid Agriculture university Rawalpindi	15-11-2023	Rawalpindi
2	Hostel warden	University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir Muzafarabad	11-10-2023	Rawalpindi

3	Cafeteria manager		BUIITEMS	25-10-2023	Rawalpindi
4	Hostel warden		University of Peshawar	2-11-2023	Peshawar
5	Mess charge	In	Quaid-e-Azam University	21-11-2023	Islamabad
6	Cafeteria charge	In	University of Karachi	14 -9-2023	Karachi
7	Hostel Warden		University of Punjab	9-1-2024	Mianwali
8	Mess charge	In	Karakoram International university Gilgit	31-10-2023	Rawalpindi
9	Mess charge	In	IBA(Sakkhar)	17-1-2024	Rawalpindi
10	Hostel warden		NUML	11-1-2024	Islamabad

To enhance the trustworthiness of the study, triangulation was employed by including multiple stakeholder perspectives including students, parents, and university authorities. This methodological triangulation allowed the study to capture a more holistic understanding of food waste behavior and increased the credibility and depth of the findings (Flick, 2023).

Data Collection

Data were collected using in-depth interviews, which allowed participants to express their views freely while ensuring coverage of key thematic areas. Separate interview cues were extracted from prior literature broadly exploring:

Food preferences, daily eating routines, meal planning, time constraints, leftover handling, and perceptions of food waste among students. From parents regarding the family values, upbringing practices, and attitudes toward food wastage in the household and among their children. Lastly, from the university staff regarding the institutional meal provision systems, food handling protocols, observed student behavior, and food waste management strategies.

Interviews were conducted bilingual in Urdu, English, or a mix of both, depending on the comfort level of participants. Each interview lasted between 30 to 40 minutes and was audio-recorded with informed consent. All recordings were transcribed verbatim for analysis (Eaton et al., 2019). The transcription process was the focus of attention as it is always critical in data analysis and central in qualitative research (Mero-Jaffe, 2011). Since the researcher was the interviewer as well as the transcriber of the interviews in the current research, thereby, it reduced compromising influences with respect to the transcript quality (Mero-Jaffe, 2011). Data collection continued until thematic saturation was achieved that is, when no new insights or themes relevant to the research questions generates. Saturation was assessed iteratively during fieldwork and analysis, ensuring that the dataset was both rich and sufficiently comprehensive to support trustworthy interpretations (Charles et al., 2015; Charmaz & Smith, 2003; Tisdell & Merriam, 2025).

Data Analyses

The transcribed data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following the six-step process proposed by Braun and Clarke (2012) which includes familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and producing the report.

The analysis was conducted inductively, allowing themes to emerge directly from the data without being shaped by predefined categories. This approach was consistent with the constructivist interpretive paradigm and allowed for the discovery of unexpected patterns and meanings in participants' narratives. The software NVIVO 14 was used to manage the data, facilitate systematic coding, and support theme development. NVIVO also enabled the comparison of patterns across participant groups, contributing to a deeper and more nuanced analysis (Feng & Behar-Horenstein, 2019).

The initial stage involved narrative preparation, during which all interview data were transcribed and key properties and characteristics were identified. In the second step, initial codes and themes were generated by interpreting, organizing, and structuring the data through a detailed, line-by-line analysis. Conceptually similar responses were grouped and coded accordingly (Blair, 2015; Corbin & Strauss, 1990; Mughal, Farida, & Khokhar, 2021). The third stage involved organizing the data according to the generated codes, identifying emerging themes, and clustering the codes into potential thematic categories. These themes were then reviewed and further refined into sub-themes, ultimately leading to the development of a thematic map for analysis. Each theme was assigned a distinct label following refinement. In the final stage, the findings were written up using supporting quotations from the raw data, and interpretations were carried out using theoretical triangulation to capture the nuances of the observed phenomena.

The analysis was conducted using NVIVO 14, which facilitated the efficient storage, organization, and presentation of large volumes of qualitative data (Feng & Behar-Horenstein, 2019). The software offered a comprehensive set of tools that enabled a deeper exploration and interpretation of patterns within the data, particularly in relation to the study's research questions. The complete process of data collection and analysis is summarized as follows:

Figure 1: Process of data collection and analysis

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Themes

A number of themes emerged from analyses of in-depth interviews and both food choice factors and consumption patterns are further categorized into several themes. The themes are presented in the tables below, followed by a detailed explanation of each theme and its corresponding sub-themes.

Table 4: Food choice factors leading to food waste behavior

Themes	Sub-themes	Description
Sensory Appeal	Taste	It is one of the most relevant factor relating to food wastage, which involves the appearance, taste and smell of the food being served. Along with that food advertisements have also defined the preferences of young consumers. Culture also plays a vital role in determining the kind of food students find appealing.
	Smell	
	Appearance	
Moods	Happy	It is also an important determinant of food waste behavior as if in the bad mood adults tend to waste more food. Ambiance also plays a vital role in determining the mood such as hygiene, company and person serving the food.
	Sad	
	Anxious	
	Angry	

Price Sensitivity	Low Cost, Low Accountability High Price, Mindful Consumption	Students tend to waste more food when it is inexpensive or subsidized, perceiving it as less valuable and feeling less guilt about discarding it. Higher food costs lead to more careful portioning, greater appreciation of food, and reduced likelihood of waste due to increased financial consciousness.
Health Consciousness	Weight consciousness Desire to look lean Peer pressure Distrust in Food Safety & Hygiene	Fear of putting on weight and appearing large is more important for young adults especially for females. To look beautiful they want slim constitution which induces food waste. Past experiences with expired or spoiled food cause hesitation and refusal to eat certain items.
Sense of Responsibility	Immature Attitudes and Careless Waste Gained Awareness Through Experience Influence of Family Grooming on Food Values	Students lack responsibility, especially younger students which results in squandering food. As students grow older they develop more consciousness.
Convenience	Instant availability Limited choices Modern lifestyle	Students eat from outside/canteens instead of university dining halls just for convenience. At home they are given fewer choices and parents make sure that the food is not wasted.

Sensory Appeal

Sensory appeal plays a crucial role in influencing food consumption and waste behaviors. The visual, olfactory, and taste qualities of food significantly affect whether individuals choose to consume or discard it. When food appears wilted, discolored, or otherwise visually unappetizing, students are more inclined to reject it. As one student observed, *“If food looks unappetizing or has an off putting smell, students are more likely to avoid it”* (Student, 4). Similarly, damaged or unattractive packaging can lead to negative perceptions about the food’s quality, prompting disposal. Unpleasant odors often interpreted as signs of spoilage or contamination further discourage consumption, even when the food may still be safe to eat. Taste is equally influential; bland, overly ripe, or poorly stored food with off-flavors often results in incomplete consumption or total waste. Reflecting on generational food habits, a parent explained, *“If a meal looks and smells good, they are more likely to enjoy it and finish it otherwise they will waste it”* (Parent, 7). These findings highlight that the sensory experience is a primary, immediate determinant in the decision to consume or discard food.

Moods

Mood fluctuations significantly impact student’s food consumption and waste behaviors. Emotional states such as stress, sadness, or anxiety often lead to altered eating patterns, including the preference for comfort or convenience foods. These emotional responses

may result in over-preparing meals or purchasing high-calorie, highly palatable items that exceed actual hunger needs, leading to increased waste. As the emotional craving subsides, the remaining food often loses appeal and is discarded. *“At times if I am upset I would skip my meal because if I feel nausea and my stomach gets upset so I try to get just liquids”* (Student, 1). University staff also acknowledged this emotional connection, stating, *“Emotional factors such as stress, anxiety, or mood swings effects student’s appetite and eating habits, leading to fluctuations in food consumption”* (Mess Incharge, 1).

Price Sensitivity

Financial conditions and price sensitivity significantly shape students' food-related behaviors, particularly in relation to perceived value. When food is inexpensive, subsidized, or prepaid as in university mess systems students tend to exhibit lower accountability and may treat food as disposable. The lack of direct, immediate financial consequence leads to over-serving, casual rejection of meals, and frequent waste. In such contexts, food is perceived as less valuable, diminishing the sense of guilt or responsibility tied to its disposal. This pattern reflects what can be termed as “Low Cost, Low Accountability.”

Conversely, when students are required to pay directly or face higher food prices, their behavior shifts notably. Financial constraints heighten awareness of food value, prompting more thoughtful portioning, avoidance of risk-prone items, and reduced plate waste. Those with limited financial resources often exhibit “High Price, Mindful Consumption” by choosing affordable yet manageable options and ensuring that food is not discarded needlessly. As a result, higher food costs either perceived or actual act as a deterrent to waste by reinforcing conscious consumption and instilling a stronger sense of personal accountability.

“If students have a lot of affordability, they tend to eat in large quantities. But if they can't consume all of it, they end up wasting the food. You can see this by looking at different tables in the cafeteria. Sometimes, one person has enough food to feed five or six people. So, yes, food waste is a significant issue” (Mess Incharge, 4).

Health Consciousness

Health consciousness also contributes to food waste by altering student’s dietary choices and portion preferences. In pursuit of fitness or ideal body image, students especially females often skip meals, restrict portions, or avoid foods deemed unhealthy, even after serving them. Additionally, the fear of overeating or consuming low-nutrient food may prompt selective eating or disposal of entire meals. *“I try to watch my portions and choose healthier options when available”* (Student, 5). Although this trend is more common among female students, increasing awareness among young males is also evident. *“Female students are usually on diet but nowadays, young male students are also conscious about weight gain and their physical appearance. Even if the charges are paid in advance, they do not bother to eat their meal from hostel mess and this issue ultimately caused the food wastage”* (Student, 9).

Sense of Responsibility

Students may experience guilt or moral discomfort when discarding food, especially in the context of global hunger and environmental sustainability. Ethical concerns around food waste among university students reflect varying levels of personal maturity and social conditioning. Many younger or undergraduate students demonstrate immature

attitudes and careless waste, showing limited moral discomfort when discarding food. Despite being aware of global hunger and environmental implications, this awareness often does not translate into responsible behavior, particularly when food is easily available or social accountability is low. However, with time and lived experiences, many students exhibit a gained awareness through experience developing a more thoughtful and responsible approach toward food consumption. Exposure to real life consequences, environmental education, or personal financial responsibilities often deepens their sense of food value, prompting waste-reducing behaviors such as portion control or repurposing leftovers.

The influence of family grooming on food values also plays a pivotal role in shaping ethical responsibility. Students raised in households that emphasized gratitude, modesty, and moral duty toward food are more likely to carry those principles into independent living. Respect for food, ingrained during early socialization, can manifest as conscious efforts to reduce waste even in challenging university environments.

“Students are aware about it but they are not concerned about it because no matter if someone is watching them or not they will throw the wrapper on the floor even if the dustbin is nearby and they waste the food in the same way” (Parent 3).

Convenience

The prioritization of convenience due to academic and social pressures strongly influences food waste behavior. Students often gravitate toward quick, ready-made meals that require minimal effort, yet these options frequently lack satisfaction or palatability, increasing the chance of leftovers. *“Convenience is a huge factor for students. We are often juggling classes, assignments, part-time jobs, and social lives, so quick and easy food options are very appealing. But this convenience can lead to waste because sometimes, the easiest options are not the tastiest or healthiest. Fast food or pre-packaged meals might be quick, but if they are not satisfying, it is easy to leave some behind”* (Student 4). The proximity of food outlets and lack of cooking facilities further reinforce dependence on convenience, which may compromise both quality and sustainability in food choices.

The need for quick or easy-to-access meals significantly influences student’s food behaviors and contribute to waste. Moreover, the availability of convenient food outlets near campus or hostels encourages students to purchase food instead of cooking. When these options fail to meet taste or quality expectations, students are more likely to leave food uneaten.

Table 5: *Food Consumption Patterns (Routine factors) leading to food waste behavior*

Themes	Sub-themes	Description
Portion Size	Fixed portion Large portion Small portion	Larger portion size leads to food waste. When the server dish out food, the portion size is larger than the requirement of students and students rarely requests to be dished out less than standard size portion.
Routine and Time Constraint	Clash with class timings Lack of time management Mess time	Fixed timings of meals and lack of disciplined time management by students leads to food waste and scheduling problem.
Spontaneous Eating-out	Irregular eating habits Eating at odd timings	Students enjoy eating from popular places. They do not plan their visits to restaurants properly so hostel food is wasted.
Social Influence	FOMO Avoidance of eating alone Social Discomfort	Undergraduate students who are the majority in universities, prefer to eat with friends. Without company they tend to waste more food. Students also enjoy eating from popular places. They do not plan their visits to restaurants properly so hostel food is wasted.

Portion Size

Portion size is a critical factor affecting food consumption and wastage among university students. Oversized servings, whether self-selected or provided by food service providers, often lead to uneaten leftovers especially when students overestimate their hunger or are influenced by external factors like food aroma, peer presence, or attractive presentations. As according to a student *“Portion sizes are a major factor in food waste, particularly for students. Often, the portions we are served at the university cafeterias are way too big for a single person”* (Student 2).

Several parents observed and reported during the interview that when students serve or are served larger than needed portions, they tend to leave part of the food uneaten. Students often feel obligated to take full meals, especially in buffet-style university dining halls or set menus, but do not always finish what is on their plate especially if they do not like the taste or if the food is not fresh. The mismatch between portion served and actual appetite results in a significant amount of avoidable waste *“Portion sizes are very significant. Serving sizes that are too large often result in students leaving food uneaten, leading to waste”* (Parent 4).

Routine and Time Constraint

Meal times significantly impact the food waste behavior of university students due to factors such as time constraints, dining hall hours, and social dynamics. During peak meal times, students may rush through their meals or select more food than they can consume, leading to increased waste. Additionally, limited dining hall hours may encourage students to stock up on food for later consumption, resulting in spoilage and

disposal of uneaten items. The university management also said that *“During peak hours, the cafeteria gets chaotic, and students might leave food behind if they do not have enough time to eat. If they spend a lot of time in line and then have to rush to class, it leads to food wastage. Their consumption often gets interrupted, contributing to more waste”* (Mess incharge 8). Routine and time constraints substantially influence food waste behavior among students, as fixed mess timings often clash with academic schedules. A lack of time management further leads to missed meals or rushed eating, resulting in increased food waste *“Sometimes, we are sitting in the cafe, enjoying our meals when we get notified about a class starting sooner than expected. In such cases, we might rush through our food or leave it unfinished, leading to waste”* (Student 5).

Spontaneous Eating-Out

Spontaneous eating out among university students can have a significant impact on their food waste behavior. When students decides to eat out impulsively, they miss the already prepared meal within hostels leading to food waste *“Students may feel pressure to conform to social norms or expectations, such as displaying wealth or indulging in exploring new foods, which often leads to wasteful behavior”* (Parent 8). This behavior disrupts regular eating habits, as students tend to skip scheduled or pre-prepared meals in favor of dining out. Over time, such irregular patterns lead to increased leftovers and untouched food, especially in hostel or mess environments where meals are pre-cooked. Additionally, eating at odd hours often late at night or in between meals can reduce appetite during regular meal times, causing students to discard untouched portions. This unpredictable pattern of consumption reflects a lack of planning and contributes directly to avoidable food waste *“We frequently order fast food from outside, such as pizzas, burgers, and fries. This option provides variety and is a popular choice among students”* (Student 2).

Social Influence

Social dining experiences often involve shared meals, group ordering, and peer influence, which can influence individual comfort and discomfort. Students may feel compelled to conform to social norms regarding eating habits and portion sizes, leading to over consumption and subsequent food waste *“Eating with friends can influence what and how much I eat”* (Student 4). Also, the desire to fit in or avoid social stigma may influence students to order more food than they can consume or to discard leftovers to align with their peers behavior. Peer influence often affects both the type and quantity of food students choose to consume, especially in communal dining environments like hostels or university mess halls. Students tend to mirror the behaviors of those around them whether that is indulging in desserts, skipping meals, or discarding leftovers. *“The social aspect of dining has a considerable impact. Meals are often seen as social events, and students may order more food than necessary when eating with friends. The focus on social interaction can sometimes overshadow practical considerations like portion control.”* (Student 3).

Additionally, the fear of missing out (FOMO) motivates students to participate in group dining or spontaneous eating-out events, even when they are not hungry or have already received meals. This can result in them abandoning scheduled or pre-served food, which ends up being wasted. Social pressure to conform or avoid seeming different often leads students to take food they might not finish, particularly when everyone else is eating a specific item or portion size.

Both food choices as well as the consumption patterns impacts the food waste behavior. It is likely that food choice factors builds attitudes while consumption patterns have direct impact on food waste behavior.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the everyday realities, perceptions, and contextual factors that shape food waste behaviors among Pakistani university students. Using a constructivist interpretive approach and guided by an extended version of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research provides rich, multi-voiced insights into how food choices and routine-based constraints influence food waste in university settings.

The findings reveal that food waste is not merely a result of poor planning or negative attitudes, but is deeply embedded in sensory preferences, emotional states, cultural grooming, social dynamics, and institutional structures. Students often waste food due to unappealing taste, smell, or appearance, as well as shifts in mood or emotional well-being. Emotional triggers such as sadness, anxiety, or even excitement frequently leads to spontaneous or comfort driven food decisions that result in squandering. Financial concerns were also salient, with students reporting a tension between maintaining a budget and compromising on quality, while health consciousness and body image pressures influenced selective eating habits that sometimes led to partial or full plate waste. Peer influence and fear of missing out (FOMO) further complicated food behaviors, as many students engaged in eating activities driven more by social cues than actual hunger or planning.

Crucially, routine and time constraints including clashes with class schedules, fixed mess timings, and lack of time management emerged as powerful drivers of food waste, highlighting a non-deliberative, habitual route to disposal behavior. The trend of spontaneous eating-out and irregular meal times also pointed to a fragmented approach to food consumption. While some students demonstrated ethical concern and awareness about waste often rooted in family upbringing or religious values many admitted to lacking a clear sense of responsibility or environmental consciousness. Additionally, distrust in food safety and hygiene standards within campus facilities contributed to the reluctance to consume available food, further increasing waste.

This study also provides an extension of Theory of Planned Behavior by incorporating food choice factors such as sensory appeal, moods, prices, convenience, health consciousness and sense of responsibility as key antecedents of student's attitudes toward food waste. These contextual and psychological drivers shape how students perceive and respond to food, influencing their likelihood to waste. By embedding these nuanced factors into the TPB framework, the research highlights the attitudinal complexity behind food related decisions in university settings.

Overall, the study underscores that food waste among university students is a multi-layered, context-driven phenomenon that cannot be addressed through awareness campaigns alone. Interventions must consider the emotional, social, and structural complexities that influence behavior. Institutional reforms, such as flexible dining systems, improved food quality, and student engagement in food waste reduction, may help create more sustainable campus food environments. Moreover, culturally grounded educational efforts that strengthen ethical responsibility and mindfulness around food can complement structural changes.

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Figure A.3: Text Query